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The Impact of Mobility, Beam Sweeping and Smart Jammers on Security Vulnerabilities of 5G Cells

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Introduction

Contribution

- Studying different jamming settings and discussing having multiple jammers in the scenario
- The behavior of 5G cell metrics in response to multi-jammer attack while having mobile users in the scenario
- Analyzing the vulnerability of 5G SSB to jamming attack

5G Network Model

- Multiple gNBs
 - To study the effect of inter-cell interference
 - Each cover a specific distance (cell area)
- Multiple UEs
 - Randomly positioned
 - Equipped with single antenna
 - UEs can freely move within the designated cell areas
 - Adding a layer of complexity to reflect the real-world scenario

Mobility Model

- Spatio-temporal parametric stepping mobility model (STEPS)
 - Preferential attachment (temporal) and location attraction (spatial)
 - Power law distribution

- Attraction of a zone: $P[D = d] = \frac{\beta}{(1+d)^\alpha}$
 - d : distance from the preferred zone, β : normalization constant, α : power law exponent
- Staying time in a zone: $P[T = t] = \frac{\omega}{t^\tau}$
 - τ : temporal preference of the node, ω : the normalization factor

Channel Model

- CDL channel
- Log-normal shadowing model
- Free space path loss (FSPL)
- Thermal noise
- Received waveform: $P_r = P_t + X_\sigma + G_t + G_r - 20\log\left[\frac{\lambda^2}{(4\pi)^2 d^2}\right]$
 - G_t : transmitter antenna gain, G_r : receiver antenna gain, λ : wavelength, d : distance from transmitter

Jammer Models

- Barrage jammer

- Transmit Gaussian noise into the whole 5G downlink bandwidth
- Jammer passes jamming signal through the CDL channel model

- Received signal from jammer: $P_j^{rx} = P_j + G_j + G_r - 20\log\left[\frac{\lambda^2}{(4\pi)^2 d_j^2}\right]$

- P_j : jamming transmit power, G_j : gain of the jammer antenna, d_j : distance from jammer

Jammer Models

- Smart Jammer
 - Transmit jamming signal to distort critical signals in 5G SSB
 - Increase energy efficiency

Performance Analysis

- Movement of UE
 - Change in path loss and RSS values
 - Varying impact of the jamming attack
- Simulation environment
 - MATLAB 5G Toolbox
 - Physical and MAC layers
 - MAC scheduler
 - MCS selection
 - HARQ, and CSI configuration
 - ...

Cell Network Metrics under Jamming

- As the distance between jammer and gNB increases, the cell throughput and goodput improve due to the reduced affected area by jammer
- While the jamming power increases from 10 to 40 dB, the cell metrics decrease rapidly
- After 40 dB, the cell goodput continues decreasing while the throughput does not change significantly
- Throughput: total number of packets including re-transmissions
- Goodput: new arrival packets
- Increasing the jamming power impacts more UEs, and through HARQ process, more packets are retransmitted
 - Less new packets: reduction in goodput

Cell Network Metrics under Jamming

- The impact of number of jammers on cell metrics
- The distance is set on 224 meters to eliminate the effect of distance
- Applying the first jammer decreases the throughput by 46.78%
- The second jammer reduces throughput by 26.12%
- Adding the third jammer only decreases the throughput by 8.16%
- The first two jammers compromised the robustness of the network

SSB Vulnerability to Jamming

- Compare the effect of barrage jammer with a smart jammer in targeting SSB in 5G
- Modulated data samples: $X(k), k = 0, \dots, n_{FFT} - 1$
- Total signal power: $P_{gNB}^{Tx} = \frac{1}{n_{FFT}^2} \sum_{k=0}^{n_{FFT}-1} |x(k)|^2$
- Received signal power per each resource element: $P_{RE}^{Rx} = \frac{|h|^2 \times P_{gNB}^{Tx}}{12 \times L \times n_{RB}}$
 - h : coefficient of the channel between gNB and UE, L : path loss, n_{RB} : number of RBs in the RG
- Adding jammer: $SJNR = \frac{P_{RE}^{Rx}}{P_j^{RE} + P_N^{RE}}$
 - P_j^{RE} : power of jammer per RE at UE, P_N^{RE} : power of noise per RE at UE

SSB Vulnerability to Jamming

- Barrage jammer:
 - To disrupt the link, it needs minimum power of $P_{j,min}^{RE}$ to reduce SJNR below the threshold γ_{th}
 - Total power: $P_j^b = 12 \times n_{RB} \times P_{j,min}^{RE}$
- Smart jammer: $P_{j,min}^{RE} = \frac{P_{RE}^{Rx}}{\gamma_{th}} - P_N^{RE}$
 - Looks for PSS and SSS to be able to locate the SSB
 - Prevents UE from connecting to gNB with less power consumption
 - Transmit jamming signal over the bandwidth of $n_{RB}^{SSB} \times 12 \times \Delta f$
 - Δf : subcarrier spacing
 - No need to transmit the jamming power during the whole frame
 - SSB burst are transmitted periodically in every two frames in 5G
 - UE cannot establish the connection if one of the PSS or SSS are not extracted
 - Total power: $P_j^s = 12 \times n_{RB}^{SSB} \times P_{j,min}^{RE}$

SSB Vulnerability to Jamming

- PBCH data or PBCH-DMRS signal
 - PSS/ SSS
 - PCI is extracted using auto-correlation
 - Robust to noise, interference, and jamming
 - Decoding PBCH instead
 - Effecting more UEs

SSB Vulnerability to Jamming

- Equalized constellation of UE PDSCH data
- Under barrage jammer
- Modulation type: 16QAM
- Jamming transmit power: 30 dBm
- RMS of EVM: 68.17%

SSB Vulnerability to Jamming

- Barrage jammer with the same jamming power
- PSS and SSS correlation
- The peak is clear, and UE can extract PCI

SSB Vulnerability to Jamming

- Smart jammer targeting the SSB
- PSS and SSS correlation
- Jamming power: 27.5 dBm
- Peak cannot be extracted

SSB Vulnerability to Jamming

- PBCH data constellation
- Jamming power: 25 dBm
- RMS EVM: 51.59%
- PCI is decoded but PBCH data is not

- Effect of beam sweeping
- Received spectrogram
- Jamming power: 25 dBm
- 8 SSB bursts during two frames
- Third SSB has higher power due to beam sweeping

SSB Vulnerability to Jamming

- Received SJNR for DM-RS in PBCH versus SSB index
- Third SSB burst is received with higher power
- Jamming power: 25 dBm
- Equalized PBCH data constellation
- Jamming power: 25 dBm
- RMS EVM: 23.36%
- More robust SSB burst
- Beam sweeping mitigates the effect of jamming

Conclusion

- Vulnerability of multi-gNB multi-user 5G under barrage and smart jammer
- UEs are mobile following STEPS mobility model
- Cell metrics under different jamming settings
- Comparison of barrage jammer and smart jammer targeting PSS, SSS, and PBCH-DMRS
- Smart jammer targeting DMRS-PBCH can prevent UE from connecting to gNB using lower jamming power compared to the case targeting PSS and SSS or barrage jammer
- Beam sweeping can make the cell selection process more robust to jammers

